

Auxetic Behavior of Needle-Punched Nonwoven Structure

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Abstract:

This study explores how needle-punched nonwoven polyester fabrics can show auxetic behavior, meaning they expand sideways when stretched instead of contracting like regular materials. The fabrics were made using fibers of two different thicknesses (6 denier and 15 denier) and three weight levels (200, 400, and 600 grams per square meter). Poisson's ratio, which measures this unique stretching behavior, was tested at different levels of strain. The results in this study showed that the nonwoven structures might be expanded in thickness when stretched, demonstrating auxetic properties. However, nonwoven fabrics made with 15-denier fibers had showed little to no auxetic effect in thickness when under tension. This research suggests that nonwoven fabrics with auxetic properties could be useful in applications like cushioning, protective clothing, and filtration materials.

Keywords: *Auxetic, Longitudinal Strain, Negative Poisson's Ratio, Needlepunched structure, protective*

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1. Introduction

Auxetic materials, which expand laterally when stretched, offer unique applications across various industries due to their enhanced mechanical properties such as energy absorption, impact resistance, and flexibility [1]. In healthcare, they improve wound dressings, stents, and orthopedic supports by offering better adaptability and comfort [2]. In protective gear, auxetic materials enhance body armor, helmets, and sportswear, providing superior shock absorption [3]. The aerospace and automotive sectors benefit from auxetic materials for crashworthiness and lightweight components [4]. Construction uses auxetic structures for vibration damping and resilient buildings [5]. In textiles, auxetic fabrics improve the fit and flexibility of smart apparel and personal protective equipment [6]. They also find use in acoustic panels, vibration damping systems, sports equipment, energy harvesting devices, and soft robotics [7]. These materials' ability to adapt to stress makes them ideal for innovative applications requiring flexibility, durability, and superior impact protection.

Nonwoven fibre networks, widely used in applications such as sensors, composites, and tissue engineering, can be engineered to exhibit auxetic behavior, i.e., a negative Poisson's ratio [1]. While most research focuses on periodic structures [8], nonwoven materials' irregular geometry offers potential for high porosity and mechanical stability [9]. Recent work explores out-of-plane auxetic polypropylene-based scaffolds for enhanced biophysical responses [10].

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

Polyester fibres of 6 denier and 15 denier were used to prepare three needle-punched nonwoven samples with areal densities of 200 gsm, 400 gsm, and 600 gsm. The needle-punching process involved 150 punches/cm² with a 12 mm depth of penetration. Fibre properties are provided in Table 1, and the sample specifications are detailed in Figure 2. All samples were produced on a Diloneedlepunch line, ensuring consistent mechanical characteristics for the study.

Table 1: Characteristics of constituent fibres

S.N.	Particulars	6D	15D
1	Suppliers	Reliance	Toray
2	Fineness (Std.), Denier	6	15
3	Fineness (Observed), Denier	7.2 ± .83	18.3 ± 1.3
4	Fibre Length (Std.), mm	64	64
5	Fibre Length (Observed), mm	62 ± 9	65 ± 8
6	Crimp/Inch	4.5 ± 0.4	3.1 ± 0.2
7	Appearance	Semi dull	Semi dull
8	Tenacity (gf/D)	4.51 ± 0.48	3.10 ± 0.24
9	Elongation (%)	48.6 ± 9.17	37.4 ± 7.4
10	Cross Sectional Shape	Circular Hollow	Circular Hollow

Table 2: Nonwoven Sample Specifications

Sr. No.	Sample Code	Areal Density (Std.), gm/m ²	Areal Density (measured), gm/m ²	Fibre Denier	Needle Density, punched/cm ²	Needle Depth Penetration, mm
1	A2D06	200	208±15	6	150	12
2	A4D06	400	416±32	6	150	12
3	A6D06	600	649±48	6	150	12
4	A2D15	200	212±23	15	150	12
5	A4D15	400	432±56	15	150	12
6	A6D15	600	675±69	15	150	12

2.2 Determination of Poisson's Ratio

Figure 1: set up on INSTRON for determination of Poisson's ratio of nonwoven samples

Poisson's ratio is a fundamental mechanical property that describes the relationship between longitudinal strain and lateral strain in a material when subjected to tensile or compressive stress. Specifically, Poisson's ratio (ν) is defined as the negative ratio of lateral strain (ϵ_{lat}) to longitudinal strain (ϵ_{long}) and is given by the formula:

$$\nu = - (\epsilon_{lat} / \epsilon_{long})$$

Where:

- ϵ_{lat} is the strain in the lateral direction (width-wise or thickness-wise contraction).
- ϵ_{long} is the strain in the longitudinal direction (stretching).

In this study, Poisson's ratio was assessed for needle-punched nonwoven structures at 5% intervals of tensile strain. As the samples were subjected to tensile tests, images were captured at predefined strain levels using digital cameras (refer to Figure 1 for the setup). These images were processed using the open-source software ImageJ to quantify width-wise and thickness-wise contractions. The central region of each sample was analyzed by counting the number of pixels corresponding to the width and thickness dimensions, providing accurate measurements of dimensional changes under strain. Photographs of the nonwoven fabric samples were captured at 0%, 5%, 10%, 15%, and 20% strain levels during the tensile tests to document the deformation process. These images were analyzed using ImageJ to determine the width-wise and thickness-wise contractions at each stage, facilitating the calculation of Poisson's ratio.

The Poisson's ratio was calculated at each interval, offering insights into the deformation characteristics of the nonwoven fabrics and their ability to exhibit auxetic behavior or lateral expansion under stretching.

3. Results and discussion

The nonwoven samples were placed under tensile load at a rate of 100 mm/min, and images were captured at 5% strain intervals, including 0%, 5%, 10%, 15%, and 20% strain, to analyze the width-wise and thickness-wise deformation. These images were processed using ImageJ software to quantify the dimensional changes in response to the applied strain. The deformation in both directions was measured to study the mechanical behavior of the needle-punched nonwoven fabrics under tensile stress. A graph was plotted between the longitudinal strain and the corresponding width-wise and thickness-wise strains (as shown in Figure 2). The analysis revealed that, as the load increased in the longitudinal direction, the nonwoven fabrics showed a negative deformation or shrinkage in the width-wise direction. This width-wise contraction was found to be nearly proportional to the longitudinal strain, indicating a consistent Poisson's ratio in that direction.

Figure 2: Plot between Longitudinal Strain and Thickness wise and Widthwise Strain

However, in the thickness direction, an increment in the thickness direction was observed, particularly in the samples made from 15 denier fibres. These structures exhibited a dramatic positive strain, meaning that the thickness of the nonwoven fabric increased as the load was applied. This behavior suggests auxetic-like characteristics in the thickness direction, where the material expands instead of contracting under tensile stress. This unique property enhances the potential applications of needle-punched nonwovens, particularly in areas requiring materials that can expand in certain directions under load, such as cushioning, protective textiles, and filtration materials. In this study, the nonwoven samples made from 6 denier fibres showed negligible changes in thickness when subjected to tensile strain, indicating a relatively stable structure in the thickness-wise direction. However, an exception was observed in the 400 gsm sample, where the thickness demonstrated a negative Poisson's ratio behaviour. This means that as tensile stress was applied in the longitudinal direction, the 400 gsm nonwoven structure from 6 denier fibres exhibited expansion in the thickness direction, contrary to the typical expansion observed in auxetic materials.

Figure 3: Plot between Longitudinal Strain and Poisson's Ratio

Figure 4: Change in Volume at various level of Longitudinal Strain

Experimental data for samples with varying densities (200, 400, 600 gsm) and fibre deniers (6, 15 denier) were analyzed for longitudinal strain and volume change. Volume change varied significantly, influenced by gsm and fibre denier, as shown in Figure 4. Sample A2D15 (200 gsm, 15 denier) had the highest mean volume change (6.59), while A6D15 (600 gsm, 15 denier) showed a negative mean (-6.57), suggesting densification. Higher gsm (600 gsm) generally led to densification, especially for thicker fibres (15 denier). Sample A4D15 showed high variability, indicating instability in intermediate gsm with higher denier.

4. Conclusions

The study demonstrated the auxetic potential of needle-punched nonwoven fabrics, specifically their ability to exhibit negative Poisson's ratio behavior in the width-wise direction and expansion in the thickness direction. The findings suggest that the material's auxetic response can be influenced by fiber denier and areal density, with thicker fibers showing auxetic-like expansion in thickness under tensile stress. These unique properties make needle-punched nonwoven fabrics suitable for various advanced applications, such as protective clothing and cushioning materials, where adaptability to tensile stress and enhanced mechanical properties are desired.

References:

- [1] R. H. Baughman, J. M. Shacklette, A. A. Zakhidov & S. Stafström, "Negative Poisson's ratios as a result of elastic instabilities," *Nature*, 392/6674 (1998) 362-365, <https://doi.org/10.1038/32660>
- [2] H. M. A. Kolken & A. A. Zadpoor, "Auxetic mechanical metamaterials," *RSC Advances*, 7/9 (2017) 5111-5129, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C6RA27333E>
- [3] K. L. Alderson & A. Alderson, "Auxetic materials for sports applications," *Procedia Engineering*, 2/2 (2007) 2883-2888, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2007.04.037>
- [4] K. E. Evans, M. A. Nkansah, I. J. Hutchinson & S. C. Rogers, "Molecular network design," *Nature*, 353/6340 (1991) 124-125, <https://doi.org/10.1038/353124a0>

- [5] W. Yang, Z. M. Li, W. Shi, B. H. Xie & M. B. Yang, "Review on auxetic materials," *Journal of Materials Science*, 39/10 (2004) 3269-3279, <https://doi.org/10.1023/B:JMISC.0000026928.93236.0d>
- [6] N. Ravirala, A. Alderson, P. J. Davies & V. R. Simkins, "Auxetic textiles for personal protective equipment," *Personal Protective Equipment and Clothing*, 44/2 (2007) 437-449, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.perpro.2007.03.044>
- [7] R. S. Lakes, "Foam structures with a negative Poisson's ratio," *Science*, 235/4792 (1987) 1038-1040, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.235.4792.1038>
- [8] H. M. A. Kolken, K. Lietaert, T. van der Sloten, B. Pouran, A. Meynen, G. Van Loock, H. Weinans, L. Scheys & A. A. Zadpoor, "Mechanical performance of auxetic meta-biomaterials," *Journal of the Mechanical Behavior of Biomedical Materials*, 104 (2020) 103658, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmbbm.2020.103658>
- [9] J. S. Soares, W. Zhang & M. S. Sacks, "A mathematical model for the determination of forming tissue moduli in needled-nonwoven scaffolds," *Acta Biomaterialia*, 51 (2017) 220-236, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actbio.2017.01.044>
- [10] Y. Yan, Y. Li, L. Song & C. Zeng, "Pluripotent stem cell expansion and neural differentiation in 3-D scaffolds of tunable Poisson's ratio," *Acta Biomaterialia*, 49 (2017) 192-203, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actbio.2016.11.048>